

Hypothesis: Effects of Reiki Practice on Biofield and Energy Regulation in Recipients

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Abstract:

Despite the existence of scientific evidence on the effectiveness of Reiki, there is still a lack of information about the proposals on how it works. Therefore, in the following paragraphs, I describe a theoretical context that supports the following hypothesis about how it might work. It is based on a review of the literature and a synthesis of information, to generate discussion and research proposals to test, refute or complement it, and thus explain scientifically an ancient practice whose benefits have been widely described.

The hypothesis I propose has to do with the fact that when the Reiki practitioner prepares to be a channel for energy transmission, they enter a state of meditation and conscious breath control, which allows them to draw Ki energy from the field (Dalmau, 2017). This energy is directed to our heart (Meartmat Institute) and from there to our palms, through intention (Baldwin et al., 2012). The Reiki practitioner stabilises their biofield with high-vibration energy (love, compassion), which synchronises with the energy emitted by the heart. Reiki practitioners intentionally direct this energy from the heart to our hands and send it to the recipient, who in turn increases their photon emission. The energy of the Reiki practitioner's biofield would become coherent with the recipient's biofield, and that energy would be directed from the receptors in the Reiki practitioner's skin (Merkel cells) to the receptors in the Merkel cells of the recipient's skin (Irma, 2010; Bataille A. et. al., 2022) and energy channels (Popp et. al., 1994, 2005). From there, through the "tunnelling" effect (Oschman, 2009; Mostajabi and Matyushov, 2023; Gray and Winkler, 2005), this energy would pass through membranes, permeate conductive tissues (collagen, proteins, water, etc.), impact DNA, and would cause changes at the transcription level (Kent, et.al, 2020), which could intervene in cellular functions that affect the recipient's well-being. It can be done remotely, as described by several authors (Yilmaz et al., 2024; MacLaren et al., 2014), and in this case, it would work through quantum entanglement (Hyland, 2004).

Key Words: Reiki, Biofield, Energy Regulation, Biophotons, Merkel Cells, Quantum Entanglement, and Heart-Brain Coherence

Reiki is a Japanese therapeutic practice considered a form of complementary and energy medicine. Its principle is based on the existence of a universal life energy called "Rei" (universal) and "Ki" (life energy), which flows through all living beings. During a session, the therapist channels this energy by placing their hands on or near the recipient's body, without physical manipulation or the use of substances. This technique was developed by Mikao Usui in 1922, following a spiritual experience on Mount Kurama, establishing the Usui Reiki Ryoho method as a practice of healing and spiritual growth.

After spreading from Japan to the West, mainly thanks to Hawayo Takata in the 1930s, Reiki was recognized in the 1990s as part of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM). The WHO includes it within manual and biofield therapies, recommending further research for its formal integration into healthcare. Countries such as Brazil incorporated it into their public health system in 2017, within the National Policy on Integrative and Complementary Practices (PNPICs) (<https://www.coren-ba.gov.br/portaria-n-8492017-inclui-novas-praticas-integrativas-e-complementares-pics-ao-sus/>).

Below is a review of the scientific literature on the subject, including the arguments and approaches that support the proposed hypothesis.

Currently, there are reports that have been developed using the scientific method, which confirm its effectiveness. such as a study demonstrating the effect of Reiki on fatigue and sleep quality in individuals with multiple sclerosis, which shows how the intervention group's scores decreased after Reiki compared to the control group, and this was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The study showed that Reiki was significantly effective in improving fatigue and sleep quality in people with multiple sclerosis (Bahçecioglu et al., 2024). Likewise, there is a controlled, prospective, randomized study that shows the effects of Reiki on pain and biochemical parameters in patients undergoing bone marrow transplantation, demonstrating that this practice is effective in controlling pain and improving the immune system response (Bektas Akpinar et al., 2025). This technique has also been applied to improve quality of life and sleep parameters, reduce cortisol and anxiety levels and biochemical parameters in individuals with heart disease (Bektas Akpinar et al., 2024), as well as reduce fatigue in hemodialysis patients, among others (Yeşil Bayülgen and Gün, 2023).

As practitioners, we know that Reiki involves a great deal of individual work, which allows us to stabilize ourselves. Reiki also integrates biofield management, meditation and breathing, and interaction with the energy that surrounds us.

Concept of the Biofield

The biofield is a term that has been accepted since 1994 and is defined as an energy field associated with living organisms that includes a combination of electrical, Effects of Reiki Practice on Biofield and Energy Regulation in Recipients N.L. Cardona Feb 2026

magnetic, electromagnetic and other forms of energy, which are generated as a result of the organism's biological processes (Rubick et al., 2015). One of the main centers of energy emission is the heart. We transmit approximately 100 photons/cm²/s (McCraty, 2015). The heart is an energy centre that can be regulated through positive thoughts, breathing and meditation. In 1991, it was discovered that the heart has 40,000 transmitting neurons, as well as proteins, which allow the heart to remember, feel and perceive (Armour 1991). Thanks to Armour's findings, neurocardiology was born, which is now widely practiced and accepted in the health sector (Cees et al., 2025). Considering that the heart emits energy, a relationship has been found between the emission of this energy and that which surrounds us, and the term "psychophysiological coherence" has been incorporated to describe the degree of harmony, order, and stability of various rhythmic activities within living organisms (McCraty et al., 2009, McCraty). An anatomical and molecular atlas of the intrinsic cardiac nervous system has now been described, using advanced imaging and analysis technologies in animal models, which allows us to increasingly understand the scope of this system in our well-being (Achanta, et al., 2020). For more than 30 years, the Heartmath Institute has been conducting studies demonstrating how brain-heart coherence can be synchronized at will through breathing, meditation, and the conscious perception of feelings of love, compassion, and gratitude (Mayoral et al., 2025).

On the other hand, Popp et al. (1994, 2002) introduced the term "quantum coherence" as well as the term "biophoton" to name the characteristic of different living beings to emit ultra-low frequency (ULF) energy. Popp (2003) suggested how biophotons interact with each other through the interconnection of variable light bands of electromagnetic fields, and explained how intracellular and intercellular communication, cell growth and differentiation, as well as interactions between biological systems, can be understood in terms of biophotons. It has now been confirmed that biophoton emission is a general phenomenon in living systems, consisting of weak photonic radiation in the spectral region from 200 to 800 nm (Benfatto et al., 2021), It has been established that the emission of biophotons corresponds to a coherent field within living organisms, which would be involved in intra- and intercellular regulation and communication (Benfatto, et al., 2021, Nevoit et al., 2023). Studies are being conducted in which there are increasingly more proposals for biological compounds that allow the transmission of biophotons, such as myelin, which provides an environment in which photon entanglement is possible. This could explain the way in which rapid responses and system synchronization occur; that is, the simultaneous response times of various organs or systems subjected to a stimulus (Liu et al., 2024). It has been determined that the efficiency of information transmission through photons in cells is faster than that of quantum computers; this is how cells use the cytoskeleton and, according to Kurian (2025), it is billions of times faster than traditional biochemical mechanisms. Through "super radiance," many molecules cooperate to emit light in a synchronized

manner, amplifying the signal, where it has been observed how tryptophan in microtubules could be involved (Kurian, 2025).

Several years ago, the hypothesis was proposed that biophotons are part of the biofield (Rubik, 2002, Rubick et al., 2015, Nevoit et al., 2023) and a model called "charge movement interaction" has been proposed, which explains the mechanism by which the biological effects of ultra-low emission frequencies on cells and molecules occur. The authors suggest that, due to the movement or rotation of charged particles in the body (protons, electrons, ions, and side groups such as amino acids), biofields are emitted into the space around the body. Likewise, biomolecules also absorb specific environmental frequencies, which induce changes in the movements of the components in such a way that living beings not only radiate but also absorb and respond to frequencies (Movaffaghi and Farsi, 2009).

Currently, biophoton emission and biofield can be measured, and their quantification has been proposed using cellular emission models (Kent, 2024), with which different types of algorithms have been developed to detect the biofield, including visualization by means of gas discharge (GDV) (Korotkov et al., 2010). This identifies the intensity of electro photonic emission in particular areas of the body, allowing diseases to be identified biometrically through mathematical modelling (Cohly et al., 2011).

Meditation: Effects on energy stabilisation and physical and mental health

Meditation is an ancient technique that is currently taught in different settings, including to children (Stapleton et al., 2024), and there are an increasing number of publications demonstrating the benefits of its practice. Such is the case of Zuniga et al. (2023), who demonstrated how the Serpina5 protein was present in the plasma of meditators and had the ability to inhibit the adhesion of the COVID-19 virus to blood cells, thus reducing the possibility of infection. Other aspects are related to improvements in diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and fibromyalgia, as well as the mental health of different individuals (Jamil et al., 2023). Recently, research (Jinich-Diamant et.al., 2025) was developed by analyzing the biological effects of a seven-day meditation retreat that integrated breathing techniques, healing rituals, and educational lectures. Through in-depth proteomic, metabolomic, and neuroimaging analyses, scientists detected significant changes in mitochondrial function, fatty acid metabolism, and immune system regulation. The results revealed a simultaneous activation of inflammatory and anti-inflammatory pathways, suggesting a dynamic process of cellular repair and enhanced biological resilience. In addition, an increase in endogenous opioids and a modulation of the nervous system were observed, linking contemplative practice to an improved capacity for physical and mental self-regulation. The study employs a predictive neuroscience approach to explain how shifts in deeply held beliefs can reconfigure the body's response to stress and pain. The immediate transformations

resulting from the retreat were primarily focused on functional connectivity and molecular activity, rather than the physical structure of the brain.

Human interaction with surrounding energy (the field)

For several years now, the relationship between electromagnetic fields and other surrounding energies in human biology has been studied. In the specific case of Schumann resonance (SR) at 7.83 Hz, Nelson (2025) suggests that cells and proteins may have adapted to these natural Earth frequencies, which would influence cellular energy levels and resting membrane potential (RMP). The absence or alteration of SR could negatively affect the functioning of the organism, as there is evidence that human brain activity depends largely on SR, suggesting a correlation between atmospheric electromagnetic frequencies and brain activity (Nelson, 2025). Similarly, Nevoit et al. (2025) conducted an exhaustive search that allowed them to compile general data on EMF, possible mechanisms of influence, and results related to the functioning of internal organs. In this review, the authors highlight how the interaction between EMF and the human body is well supported, with the most evident action being its influence on the nervous system. They also highlight how SR influences functional indicators of the cardiovascular system, such as heart rate and blood pressure. In this regard, the authors mention that low-frequency SR seems to reduce the risk of acute myocardial infarction, although it could promote the development of chronic kidney disease (Nevoit et al., 2025, Fernández et al., 2020).

On the other hand, research is being conducted on the influence that humans may have on solar and geomagnetic activity. The Global Coherence Initiative (GCI) is an international scientific project that studies the interaction between humans and the Earth's magnetic field, as well as the effect of collective intention in promoting peace and harmony. The project uses the Global Coherence Monitoring System (GCMS), which consists of a network of magnetometers distributed at various sites around the Earth, designed to measure geomagnetic and resonant frequencies, such as Schumann resonances, Alfvén waves, and other field line resonances. The authors report that some collective behaviors, as well as different human physiological rhythms, are influenced or synchronized in some cases with the environment. The GCI proposes that the Earth's magnetic fields function as an interconnection mechanism, with the capacity to transmit information non-locally between all living systems (McCraty R and Abdullah, 2021). At this same institute, studies are also being conducted on how humans could synchronize our hearts with the energy fields of other people's hearts, and even those of animals (MacCraty, 2015), which would demonstrate the energetic influence that could be exerted on people.

There is a wide variety of energies around us that interact with our own individual or collective energy and, according to the above, can influence ours, both individually and collectively. Within this energy that surrounds us are biophotons (Rubick,

2002), described in previous paragraphs, whose emission by human beings had already been extensively researched (Cohen and Popp, 2003), as well as their interaction between living organisms (Popp and Chang, 2000). Furthermore, based on the findings of Dr. F.A. Popp together with Dr. Klaus Peter Schlebusch, for several years now, it has been suggested that biophotons could be a modern interpretation of the traditional concept of "Qi" (Ki in Japan) or life force, described in Chinese medicine (Dalmau-Santamaria, 2013).

HOW DO WE RECEIVE AND TRANSMIT THE REIKISTS OF THAT SURROUNDING ENERGY?

This energy is deposited in "the energy field". "The Field" is a network in which living and non-living beings are immersed. This network is made up of electromagnetic fields from the sun, the Earth (Schumann Resonance) and all living beings. Reiki practitioners must be in contact with the energy field, and this was initially studied by Baldwin et al. (2013). The authors recorded that a Reiki practitioner was subjected to strong magnetic shielding in a SQUID device (Superconducting Quantum Interference Device - Ultra-weak Magnetic Field Meter) when the ability to emit energy was being evaluated. The Reiki practitioner lost the ability to emit energy while in the device, leading the authors to suggest that energy healing would be stimulated by tuning into external environmental radiation (Baldwin et al., 2013). On the other hand, it has been demonstrated how Reiki practitioners can direct energy and "charge" our hands with electromagnetism at will, with the power of energy of intention (Connor et al., 2021; Rubik and Jabs 2017). This is how we can increase the amount of blood in our fingers when we intentionally "connect" to the field, which was demonstrated by imaging using a laser scanner (Baldwin et al., 2007). Studies show how people have the ability to use intention to modify biological aspects, both in plants (Shiah et al., 2021) and in human cells. It has been observed that intentional water can have effects on the movement of cancer cells, which would decrease their ability to metastasise (Yu et al., 2025).

One possible way to intentionally receive and emit energy from biophotons would be through the Merkel cells described by Irmak (2010). It has been suggested that these cells act directly by receiving and emitting photons to the atmospheric circuit and the Earth, promoting such energy exchange. Merkel cells contain light-sensitive molecules, such as *flavins* or *porphyrins*, which absorb photons in both directions. The melanin present in neighboring cells of the epidermis in light capture generates chemical or electrical signals that affect Merkel cells with sensitivity to specific wavelengths. Likewise, they could be associated with specialized nerve fibers called Merkel disc endings involved in the transmission of ultra-weak photon emission to the central nervous system (Bataille et al., 2022). Once inside the organism, energetic cellular communication could take place through a set of structures called the "living matrix". This is defined as the continuous molecular tissue of the organism, formed by fascia, other connective tissues, extracellular matrices, integrins, cytoskeletons, nuclear matrices, and DNA. Biopolymers or

fundamental extracellular, cellular, and nuclear substances constitute a charge reserve throughout the body that can maintain electrical homeostasis. Some research has emphasized the importance of charge transfer in relation to the elimination or neutralization of free radicals delivered to injury sites during and after oxidative burst (Oshman 2009).

Since the late 1960s and early 1970s, some clues have emerged as to how this energy could be transported and stored. Fröhlich proposed a model that explains energy transmission in biological systems, where the energy supplied could generate coherent electrical vibrations that would allow for orderly energy storage and, in turn, share it over long distances within the system (Fröhlich, 1968). Additionally, it is known that electrons generate biophotons through biochemical reactions as a form of communication or cellular regulation within living organisms (Lauck, et al., 1992). This form of communication could be carried out through the effect known as "tunnelling," which consists of electrons being transferred through membranes along chains of protein molecules that could be separated from each other by distances of the order of nanometers (1 nm = 10^{-9} m). Different tunnelling times have been calculated for some intermolecular distances of proteins (Gray and Winkler, 2005), and this effect is known to influence the efficiency of energy transfer. Thus, for example, electrons can be transported by this effect between some cofactor molecules on a millisecond scale of $\approx 20 \text{ \AA}$ (Oshman, 2009), which confers high efficiency in energy transmission. This transmembrane energy transmission could similarly affect DNA. There are reports explaining how DNA would function as a fractal antenna, capable of transmitting or receiving electromagnetic radiation, characterized by being compact, multiband and having excellent performance at various frequencies. This fractal behavior could be related to its role in processes such as genetic transcription and repair. According to the above, DNA would not only be a storehouse of genetic information but could also play a more active role in the reception and transmission of electromagnetic signals in the human body, and its role in transcription could also be influenced by such signals (Blank and Goodman, 2011). This could then explain the events recorded by Kent et al. (2020), who measured the effect of the laying on of hands by Reiki practitioners and non-practitioners on mouse intervertebral cells. The amount of collagen and aggrecan (cartilage connecting protein) was measured in the cells to establish whether there were differences between cells subjected to Reiki practitioners and non-practitioners. In this same study, the emission of biophotons emitted by Reiki practitioners and non-practitioners in ten-minute sessions on the cells was also evaluated over three consecutive days. The results showed that in the cells treated by the Reiki practitioner, the expression of collagen and aggrecan increased *in vitro*, and, in addition, the Reiki practitioners increased their biophoton emission when compared to the non-Reiki control. Based on the above, it is possible

that the emission of biophotons by practitioners on intervertebral cells could affect DNA with its corresponding genetic transcription into connecting proteins.

The above is expected to support this hypothesis, which must be tested and needs to be enriched in future scientific findings.

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